

Work in Progress: ESPECIFICA++, a DSL for Developing the Competency of Formal Specification in Computer Programming Education

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Abstract—Competence in Formal specification is a key skill with which Computing Engineering students often face significant challenges. In this paper, we propose ESPECIFICA++, a domain-specific language (DSL) embedded in the programming language C++ that allows for the description of executable specifications, resulting in a promising tool for fostering the development of formal specification skills among students. Using ESPECIFICA++, students can describe aspects such as preconditions, postconditions, and algorithm invariants. These descriptions then become executable objects that can be validated against sets of test cases, as if they were programs. The paper describes the development process and the current stage in the development of the DSL, outlines the main features of ESPECIFICA++, and conducts a preliminary evaluation of its applicability and usefulness.

Keywords—Computer Programming Education, Formal Methods Education, Algorithmics, Program Specification, DSL

I. INTRODUCTION

Programming is a core subject in many university studies in Computing, Software, and Computer Engineering [1], as well as in other engineering disciplines. Among all the specific competencies that students in this subject must acquire, the most important is the ability to develop error-free programs that correctly solve the problems for which they were designed. Therefore, in our opinion, and that of others [2], computer engineering students must have at least a basic competence in formal specification. However, our experience teaching introductory algorithm courses has shown that students face significant difficulties in acquiring basic competencies related to this topic (this concern has also been observed by others, e.g., [3]).

To mitigate this situation, we are currently working on an educational strategy focused on *executable specifications*. Our proposal is for students to be able to construct executable specifications that can be validated using the same sets of test cases they use to validate their code. To implement this strategy, we have started by defining a domain-specific language (DSL) [4] for algorithm specification, based on a subset of the predicate logic formalism that we currently use in our introductory algorithm courses [5]. This DSL, which we have named ESPECIFICA++ (an acronym for *Executable SPECIFICAtions in C++*), has been implemented as an embedded language in C++ (the primary language used in our courses). Utterances in ESPECIFICA++ are *executable*. It means that, using ESPECIFICA++, students can *build* predicates and other specification-related expressions as executable artifacts. With this, our goal is for students to change their perception of specifications, viewing them as fully equivalent to programs, as objects that can be executed, experimented with, and validated using meaningful test cases.

After discussing some works related to ours (section II), this paper describes the development process and the current stage in the development of ESPECIFICA++ (section 0). It also provides an initial qualitative evaluation (section 0). Finally, it presents some conclusions and future work directions (section IV).

II. RELATED WORK

There are multiple works that propose strategies to facilitate the development of formal specification competencies among students. For example, in [6] *Dafny*, a programming language that integrates formal specifications into its type system excluding programs that cannot be proven to meet their specification [7], is proposed as a vehicular language in an introductory algorithms course. In [8], an educational strategy is also proposed, based on *Dafny*, for learning formal methods. This strategy starts with programs and advocates for the progressive incorporation of assertions (preconditions, postconditions, invariants). In [9], also in the context of *Dafny*, mechanisms are proposed for correcting specifications that are not satisfied by the programs, which is useful in scenarios where the program is considered correct rather than the specification. In [10], the lack of support from programming environments for languages where programs incorporate their specifications is identified as a key factor for success in education, and the integration of the PEST language, a language similar to *Dafny*, with the Eclipse platform is proposed.

While the purpose of these strategies is similar to ours, the difference lies in that we promote executable specifications that can be developed and validated independently of the programs and later easily integrated with them. In this way, our approach is somewhat complementary to the use of languages that support automatic verification in compile-time: with our approach, the student can crystallize the specifications with the help of a mainstream programming language and later verify their programs using more specialized languages (e.g., the aforementioned *Dafny* and PEST).

III. THE ESPECIFICA++ DSL

In this section we start by describing the process that we are carrying out in the development of ESPECIFICA++, and in its incorporation to our education settings (subsection III.A), and we describe the current version of the DSL (subsection III.B).

A. Development process

¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia. illustrates the process followed in the development of ESPECIFICA++. According to this process, the development begins with an initial provision of the operational DSL (*DSL provision* activity). Next, the *Instructor-driven DSL Refinement* activity is iterated, during which the team of instructors evaluates and refines the DSL to align it with their educational needs. Once a DSL is available that meets the educational requirements defined by the instructors, it is further iteratively refined through a controlled use with students (*Student-driven DSL Refinement*). In the final stage of the process, during the *DSL Enactment* activity, the DSL is implemented in the various programming courses taught by the instructors.

Fig. 1. Development process of the ESPECIFICA++ DSL

Currently, we have completed the *DSL provision* activity and conducted the first iteration of the *Instructor-driven DSL Refinement* activity. Below, we describe the features of the designed DSL. The next section, in its turn, will focus on the results obtained during the first refinement iteration.

B. The DSL

The ultimate purpose of ESPECIFICA++ is to define predicates and other types of expressions. The most basic predicates and expressions are constructed with the primitives `pred` and `exp`, which are used on, respectively, *boolean* and arbitrarily typed C++ expressions. In addition, predicates can be combined using logical connectives: AND (&&), OR (||), NOT (!), implication (>>), and equivalency (`equiv`). In the same way, expressions of the appropriated types can be combined with comparison operators (`==`, `!=`, `<`, `>`, `<=`, `>=`) to yield predicates, and with arithmetic operators (`+`, `-`, `*`, `/`, `%`) to yield new expressions.

In addition to these basic facilities, the core of ESPECIFICA++ consists of notation for predicates and quantified expressions supported by predicate calculus-based formalisms [5]. All these quantifications follow a common format:

$$Q\langle typeSpecs \rangle (qvars).range(inf,sup)(.filter(F))?.ev(V)$$

where $(...)?$ represents *optionality*. Here:

- Q represents the type of quantification.
- $typeSpecs$ explicitly defines the type of the values in the quantification range and, if necessary, the type of the values returned by the quantified expression V indicated in the ev clause.
- $qvars$ is the list of *quantified variables*. These variables must be explicitly declared using the `var` primitive (`var(T, v)` declares a quantified variable v of type T), and they can be accessed with the `*` prefix operator.
- The `range` clause determines the variation range for these variables (inf and sup are, respectively, the lower and upper bounds, and they can be C++ expressions, quantified variables, or ESPECIFICA++ expressions).
- Finally, the optional `filter` clause can introduce a predicate F to take only specific value assignments to quantified variables into account (those for which F evaluates to *true*).

The operational reading of these quantifications is as follows: (i) to generate all possible value assignments within the quantification range to the quantified variables; (ii) if the filter predicate F is specified, to discard all assignments for which F evaluates to *false*; (iii) for each non-discarded assignment, to evaluate the quantified predicate or expression V ; and (iv) to combine the results of the evaluations to produce the result of the quantified predicate or expression, depending of the particular quantification Q used. For this purpose, ESPECIFICA++ introduces the following types of quantifications:

- *Universal* ($Q = \text{forall}$) and *existential* ($Q = \text{exists}$) quantifications, which makes it possible to construct predicates. A `forall` predicate evaluates to *true* if all evaluations of V are *true*. In its turn, an `exists` predicate evaluates to *true* when at least one of the evaluations of V is *true*. In these quantifications, `yield` is used as the *ev* clause, and only the type of the values in the quantification range is specified in *typeSpecs*.
- *Sum* ($Q = \text{sum}$), *product* ($Q = \text{prod}$), *minimization* ($Q = \text{mini}$), *maximization* ($Q = \text{maxi}$) and *count* ($Q = \text{number}$) expressions. A `sum` expression adds all the results produced by the evaluation of V , a `prod` multiplies all these results, a `mini` expression finds the minimum of these values, and a `maxi` expression finds the maximum. In all these expressions it is necessary to specify in *typeSpecs*, first the type of the values in the range and then the type returned by V . Additionally, `val` is used as the *ev* clause. Concerning a `number` expression, V must be a predicate, and the result is the number of values for which V evaluates to *true*. Thus, the type of V is not required in *typeSpecs*, and `yield`, instead of `val`, is used as the *ev* clause.

0 provides examples of all these quantifications. The expressions are also commented with the usual predicate calculus notation used in program specification [5].

```

int a[] = { 7,2,5,10,21 };
int n = 5;
var(int, i);
/*  $\forall i:0 \leq i < n: a[i] > 0$  */
auto p1= forall<int>(i).range(0, n-1).
        yield(pred(a[*i] > 0));

/*  $\exists i:0 \leq i < n: a[i] \% 2 = 0$  */
auto p2= exists<int>(i).range(0, n-1).
        yield(pred(a[*i] \% 2 == 0));

/*  $\sum i:0 \leq i < n \wedge a[i] \% 2 = 0: a[i]$  */
auto e1 = sum<int, int>(i).range(0, n - 1).
        filter(pred(a[*i] \% 2 == 0)).
        val(exp(a[*i]));

/*  $\prod i:0 \leq i < n \wedge a[i] > 5: a[i]$  */
auto e2 = prod<int, int>(i).range(0, n - 1).
        filter(pred(a[*i] > 5)).
        val(exp(a[*i]));

/*  $\min i:0 \leq i < n \wedge a[i] \% 2 = 0: a[i]$  */
auto e3 = mini<int, int>(i).range(0, n - 1).
        filter(pred(a[*i] \% 2 == 0)).
        val(exp(a[*i]));

/*  $\max i:0 \leq i < n: a[i]$  */
auto e4 = maxi<int, int>(i).range(0, n - 1).
        val(exp(a[*i]));

/*  $\# i:0 \leq i < n: a[i] > a[0]$  */
auto e5 = number<int>(i).range(0, n - 1).
        yield(exp(a[*i] > a[0]));

```

Fig. 2. Examples of quantified predicates and expressions in ESPECIFICA++ (the ESPECIFICA++ constructs are highlighted)

Since ESPECIFICA++ is embedded in C++, students can take advantage of C++'s own abstraction mechanisms. For example, C++ functions to introduce symbols for predicates and expressions. However, it should be noted that if parts of quantifications are abstracted, it will be necessary to pass quantified variables as arguments. To describe the types of these parameters, ESPECIFICA++ introduces the `Var<T>` primitive.

Finally, all the predicates and expressions constructed in ESPECIFICA++ can be *executed*. To do this, it is enough to append the invocation operator `()` to these predicates and expressions. For this purpose, it is noticeable that, in each invocation, the values of the program variables will be those values *at the time predicates or expressions were constructed*. If the variables change later, these changes will not be reflected in the constructed predicates and expressions.

PRELIMINARY EVALUATION

To assess the applicability of ESPECIFICA++ for building executable specifications, we have put ourselves in the shoes of our students, tackling a prototypical iterative algorithm design problem (subsection III.C). Then, we have carried out a qualitative analysis of the main findings gathered during this experience (subsection III.D).

C. Case study

We have explored how our students could use ESPECIFICA++ in the solution of the *longest constant segment problem*, an instance of the *longest segment problem* [11]. This problem consists of finding, given a non-empty vector of integers, the longest *constant segment* (i.e., sequence of consecutive elements where the same element is repeated).

Our students should begin the development of the algorithm by specifying its *precondition* (the condition that the input data must meet) and its *postcondition* (the condition that the results must satisfy). To address these aspects, our students could take advantage of C++ functional abstraction mechanisms to provide useful definitions, expressed in ESPECIFICA++ (0).

```
int max_len_cons_seg(int a[], int n) {
  /*PRE:*/assert(0 < n && n <= N);

  int i = 1;
  int len = 1;
  int resul = 1;

  /*INV:*/ assert(max_lcs(a, i, resul)());
  /*INV:*/ assert(last_cons(a, i, len)());
  /*INV:*/ assert(0 < i <= n);
  /*BOUND:*/ assert((n - i) >= 0);
  while (i < n) {
    if (a[i] == a[i - len]) {
      i++;
      len++;
      if (len > resul) resul = len;
    }
    else { i++; len = 0;}

    /*INV:*/ assert(max_lcs(a, i, resul)());
    /*INV:*/ assert(last_cons(a, i, len)());
    /*INV:*/ assert(0 < i <= n);
    /*BOUND:*/ assert((n - i) >= 0);
  }
  /*POST:*/assert(max_lcs(a, n, resul)());
  return resul;
}
```

Fig. 3. Annotated implementation.

Once the problem to be solved is specified, the next step to be carried out by our students should be to devise an efficient solution. For this purpose, they can firstly provide a suitable *invariant* that characterizes the behavior of the iterative process (i.e., the conditions that must be met by the states at the beginning of the process, as well as after each iteration) [5]. To facilitate the specification of this invariant, students could provide additional abstractions (0). In addition, they can provide a *bound condition*, to check algorithm termination.

```
auto cons_seg (int a[], Var<int> i, Var<int> j){
  var(int, k);
  /*  $\forall k: i \leq k \leq j: a[i] = a[k]$  */
  return forall<int>(k).range(i, j).
    yield(pred(a[*i] == a[*k]));
}

auto max_lcs(int a[], int n, int resul){
  var(int, i);
  var(int, j);
  /*  $\max i, j: 0 \leq i \leq j \leq n \wedge \text{cons\_seg}(a, i, j): (j-i)+1$  */
  return
  exp(resul) ==
  maxi<int, int>(i, j).
  range(0, n - 1).
  filter(pred(*i <= *j) && cons_seg(a, i, j)).
  val(exp((*j - *i) + 1));
}
```

Fig. 4. Abstractions for the specification

Once students clarify the algorithm's concept and establish the invariant, the implementation becomes straightforward. 0 shows a possible implementation, annotated with the conditions previously described. To include the annotations, the `assert` macro from C++'s `cassert` library is used.

```
auto last_cons(int a[], int i, int len) {
    var(int, k);
    /* (∀k:i≤k≤j:a[i-len]=a[k])∧
       (i-len =0 ∨ a[i-len-1] ≠ a[i-len] ) */
    return forall<int>(k).range(i-len, i-1).
        yield(pred(a[i-len] == a[*k])) &&
            pred(i-len == 0 || a[i-len-1] != a[i-len]);
}
```

Fig. 5. Abstractions for the invariant.

D. Qualitative analysis

Based on the use of ESPECIFICA++ in our case study, we have conducted a preliminary analysis of its suitability for our educational strategy based on a SWOT (*Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats*) analysis [12]. Below, we summarize the main findings obtained:

- *Strengths*: (i) *Goal fulfillment*: All participants in the project agreed that ESPECIFICA++ meets the goal of providing a DSL that enables the construction of executable specifications. (ii) *Alignment with formal notation*: It reasonably reflects the formal notation used in introductory algorithm courses, facilitating the transition from formal to practical approaches. (iii) *Integration with C++*: Its close relationship with C++ can allow students to integrate specifications directly into implementations using tools like `assert` and leverage C++'s abstraction mechanisms. This also has the advantage that students do not have to switch to a more specific programming language, which supports formal assertions, but can continue to use a mainstream programming language (C++, in our case). (iv) *Conciseness*: ESPECIFICA++ has a limited number of constructs, making it easier to learn and apply in introductory courses. (v) *Incremental validation*: Predicates and expressions can be developed and incrementally validated by students through test cases, promoting gradual learning.
- *Weaknesses*: (i) *Limited error diagnostics*: Being embedded in C++, error messages generated by incorrect specifications resemble those of C++, which can be confusing for students as they are not tailored to ESPECIFICA++. (ii) *Difficulty diagnosing execution errors*: Incorrect specifications can lead to execution errors that are hard to diagnose for less experienced students. (iii) *Confusing variable behavior*: The behavior of variables in predicates and expressions, where changes in program variables are not reflected automatically, can be perplexing—particularly in distinguishing between program variables and quantified variables. (iv) *Potential inefficiency in the execution of quantifications*: Quantifications explore all possible assignments of values in the range to the quantified variables. Thus, executable specifications will be inherently more inefficient than final implementations, an aspect that will have to be considered in the selection of test batteries for ESPECIFICA++'s executable specifications.
- *Threats*: (i) *Resistance from formalist approaches*: The idea of treating specifications as executable programs may not be well-received by those educators who favor more formalist approaches, potentially leading to resistance against adopting ESPECIFICA++. (ii) *Dependency on C++*: ESPECIFICA++'s dependence on C++ may limit its usefulness for educators and students who prefer other programming languages, hindering its adoption outside of C++ environments.
- *Opportunities*: (i) *Development of formal specification skills*: The difficulty faced by students in mastering formal specification is a key opportunity for ESPECIFICA++, as it provides a practical tool to improve this competency, which has traditionally been challenging in introductory algorithm courses.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we have described ESPECIFICA++, a DSL embedded in C++ that allows students to create executable specifications. In our preliminary evaluation, we have verified that the DSL allows for the effective creation of executable specifications at the level required in an introductory algorithmics course. We have also identified certain weaknesses and threats, which we are working to resolve and plan to address in the future. For this purpose, we are conducting new iterations of the *Instructor-driven DSL refinement* activity: we are currently exploring the creation of similar DSLs in other frequently used object-oriented programming languages, particularly Java and Python, and we are also working on approaches to improve error diagnostics, concerns with variables, and potential inefficiency issues. In the immediate future, we plan to conduct an educational efficacy evaluation of the approach (*Student-driven DSL refinement* activity). Concerning *DSL enactment*, we aim to develop a repository of ESPECIFICA++ specification activities and deploy these activities into an online automated judge system (e.g., DomJudge [13]) for student use.

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